

A METHODOLOGICAL MODEL OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN ART POTTERY COURSES

¹Ibraimov Xolboy Ibragimovich, ²Jakhongir Begijonov

¹Director of the Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyozzi. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

²Teacher of the department of “Art and Engineering Graphics” of Andijan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8396921>

Abstract. *The article is aimed at the formation of students' creative competence necessary to create an image in pottery, i.e. imaginative thinking, creative imagination, artistic observation, visual memory, emotional attitude to the depicted phenomenon, associative thinking, specific thinking, sensorimotor qualities, self-criticism, in accordance with their goals and objectives, logical dependence of direct and relevant tasks. the information is given aimed at developing the content of the educational process, including theoretical and practical courses, structured taking into account.*

Keywords: *creative imagination, artistic observation, visual memory, decorative and applied art, didactic principles, the principle of science, the principle of systematicity, the principle of consistency.*

The development of creative competence among students means the ability not only to perform technologically correct things in the decorative arts, but also to create creatively valuable products.

Formation of interest in artistic heritage occurs only if the teacher himself has these abilities. It follows from this that it is necessary to train a specialist who not only knows the theory and history of art, has craftsmanship, knows the methodology of teaching the subject, but also has a deep and clear understanding of the process of forming a creative image.

For this, imaginative thinking, creative imagination, artistic observation, perception, visual memory and other components of creative competence for decorative and practical activities, such as emotional response to the depicted phenomenon, associative, abstract thinking, originality of thinking, criticism, efficiency, sensorimotor qualities, such as self-control, must be developed.

The methodological model developed by us includes the following conditions for the development of creative competencies of students in the process of teaching artistic ceramics:

- creating problematic situations when setting tasks;
- performance of tasks through their acceptable complexity;
- direct personal interactions with students in teaching;
- the process of personal creative activity of students;
- creation of motivational needs for decorative and practical activities for students, in particular, pottery;
- division of tasks to solve the figurative composition of pottery products in the formation of educational tasks;
- directing the technological process to the implementation of figurative content in students' works.

The structure of the integrated methodological model developed by us ensures a close connection between teaching and the development of creative competence.

The course "Artistic ceramics" sets the goals of teaching students and developing creative competence of the individual through artistic ceramics as a type of decorative and practical art.

The educational, educational and developmental tasks of the stylistic model are aimed at forming the creative competence of students necessary for creating an image in ceramics, i.e. imaginative thinking, creative imagination, artistic observation, visual memory, emotional reaction to the depicted event, associative thinking, specific thinking, sensorimotor qualities, self-criticism.

In accordance with the goals and tasks of the course, the content of the educational process was developed, which includes theoretical and practical courses, which are structured directly and taking into account the logical connection of the relevant tasks. It is reflected in the experimental curriculum of the artistic ceramics course.

The problem of developing creative competence with the help of various tools of fine art has been considered many times in various studies.

In order to create the most favorable conditions for the formation of a creative personality, the development of the most effective methods of formation and development of creative competence in the educational process is an object of constant study of pedagogy.

We studied and analyzed the didactic principles of teaching and personal development used in pedagogy in order to create an optimal methodological system for the development of creative competence in pottery classes.

The analysis of scientific and methodological literature made it possible to determine the most optimal principles that help to organize the pedagogical process and fulfill the tasks of developing the creative competence of students.

Functions of teaching methods in modern didactics are usually divided into two groups. The first group consists of functions related to the goals and functions of the educational process (educational, educational and developmental), and the second consists of management functions of teaching methods (stimulation, organization and control).

Didactic principles, that is, the principle of science, the principle of clarity, the principle of systematicity and consistency, the principle of consciousness and creative activity, the principle of educational and developmental education, the principle of the power of mastering knowledge, skills, skills, the principle of the connection of education with life.

The principle of individuality, the principle of taking into account collectiveness and individual abilities, the principle of the existence of education with sufficient complexity are interrelated and integrated with each other. In this regard, they can be presented as a system of principles.

Didactic principles based on a methodological system and subject to the general goal of developing creative competence determine the content, forms, teaching methods and tools of lessons.

Bringing an active approach to student education to the fore, complicating educational tasks related to technology improvement and setting new tasks, the educational system requires constant updating of methods of solving them.

The application of the didactic principles that we have considered in pottery classes together with special methods of teaching aimed at developing the creative competence of students ensures the optimal performance of educational tasks.

There are a number of shortcomings in the current program in artistic ceramics. For example, in the practice of teaching students, the main focus is on the technical side of performance.

When submitting the educational material, tasks are set for mastering the technology of performing various types of artistic ceramics, that is, making volumetric forms in the form of reliefs, small plastics, veins using certain modeling methods.

The program includes tasks such as "Round-shaped container in the spiral modeling technique", "Spherical container in the SHAPING modeling technique", "Tile", "Folk", "Making a plaster mold".

Creative competence is developed by revising the material in defining educational tasks from a specific perception through a personal meaningful view.

Complexity of tasks to the extent that students understand the figurative content of the work is an important factor in the process of developing students' creative competence.

The stepwise complexity of the technological process (hand molding, molding on the potter's wheel, making models, filling and casting in a plaster mold) is also a complicating task. Certain ceramic materials are used in the study of various technologies of artistic ceramics.

Taking into account the possibilities of these materials and the specific features of their technological processing, the students have the task of creating images in ceramic products.

It is also a complex task to study the decorative possibilities of the pottery material and the different ways of decorating raw and malleable products. By consistently and comprehensively studying decorative techniques and techniques, students learn to complement and complicate an image with decorative elements.

Taking into account the individual characteristics of each student helps to determine the directions of training for each of them and to distinguish the stages of work where difficulties are observed:

- creating a sketch of a ceramic product that expresses the attitude to the transmitted image;
- creating a sketch in a three-dimensional image (in clay);
- consistent construction of the form while observing the technological process of pottery production;
- compatibility of external and internal content.

In the context of the development of students' creative competencies, we identified the following shortcomings of pottery in the field of "Applied Art (art pottery)" at Gulistan University:

- an underdeveloped methodological system aimed at developing creative competence;
- the curriculum is mainly aimed at acquiring technological knowledge, skills and qualifications for the processing of art pottery materials (training in modeling techniques, familiarization with product production technology, analysis of the quality of technical performance of the product), which harms the image of educational and creative tasks;
- technological training is not closely related to understanding the specific features of artistic and plastic language of ceramics.

A methodical model aimed at developing the creative competence of students of "Applied Art (Art Pottery)" faculties in the process of creating an image in ceramics teaches the selection of certain methods, methods and teaching forms that help to optimize cognitive activity in the field of artistic pottery, and an active approach to learning.

REFERENCES

1. Булатов С.С., Мансуров Ў. Миллий меъморчиликда наққошлик фалсафаси. – Т.: Фан, 2005. -152 б.
2. Булатов С.С., Юлдашев Х.А. Касб-хунар коллежларида меъморий безак санъати йўналиши бўйича «Ганч ўймакорлиги» фанидан экспериментал намунавий ўқув дастури. –Т.: ЎМКХТРИ, 2003.- 15 б.
3. Булатов.С.С, Толипов.Н. Гўзаллик фалсафаси (Монография). - Т.: Fan va texnologiya. 2008, - 128 б.
4. Булатов С.С., Аширова М.О. Наққошлик қисқача луғати. Т.: Қомуслар бош таҳририяти. 1992, - 47 б. 127
5. Гуломов С.С., Булатов С.С. Шарқона “Уста-шогирд” одоби /Проф.Қ.Аллаев таҳрири остида. Т., 2000. – 61 б.
6. Булатов С.С., Юлдашев Х.А., Турсуналиев Н.Ю. Кулолчилик санъати / Қўлланма. - Т.: Низомий номли ТДПУ, 2002. -31 б.
7. Булатов С.С., Салимов С., Мухторов А. Шердор мадрасаси безакларининг сирли олами. – Т.: Талқин, 2007.
8. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –Т., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
9. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
10. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
11. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
12. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
13. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
14. Ibragimov, X. I., U. A. Yo'ldoshev, and X. Bobomirzayev. "Pedagogik psixologiya." O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent (2009).